

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA INTERACTION AND DIGITAL PROMOTION ON TIKTOK ON ADIDAS PURCHASE DECISIONS AMONG GEN Z IN PALU CITY

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Received : 20 November 2025

Published : 17 January 2026

Revised : 01 December 2025

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/morfai.v6i2.4948>

Accepted : 25 December 2025

Publish Link : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/MORFAI/article/view/4948>

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of social media interactions through the TikTok *Shop feature* and digital promotions on purchasing decisions for Adidas products with *brand awareness* as an intervening variable among Generation Z in Palu City. The research method uses a quantitative approach with *purposive sampling techniques* and data processing through PLS-SEM 4.0. The results show that social media interactions and digital promotions have a positive and significant effect on *brand awareness* and purchasing decisions. *Brand awareness* also has a significant effect on purchasing decisions and mediates the relationship between social media interactions and digital promotions on purchasing decisions. These findings confirm that interaction-based promotional strategies and creative content on TikTok are effective in increasing *brand awareness* and driving consumer purchasing decisions.

Keywords: *Brand Awareness* , *Social Media Interaction*, *Purchase Decision*, *Digital Promotion*, *TikTok Shop*.

INTRODUCTION

Social media has become an essential part of modern society. Platforms like TikTok offer short, visual, and interactive content that captures users' attention, serving not only as entertainment but also as an influence on communication patterns, social interactions, identity formation, and consumer preferences and behavior (Fernanda & Dwita, 2024). Through *e-commerce features* and digital promotional strategies, social media plays a role in increasing *brand awareness* , shaping perceptions, and influencing product purchasing decisions, including fashion brands like Adidas.

Figure 1 Adidas Product Division Revenue Growth and Share for Q2 2025

The rapid growth phenomenon in Adidas' product division in the second quarter of 2025, with footwear recording a 9% increase, apparel 17%, and accessories 7%, demonstrates the success of their marketing strategy. Adidas dominates the footwear segment with 58% of total sales, followed by apparel (34%) and accessories (8%).

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This condition illustrates how their product strategy focused on the *footwear category* has successfully driven their revenue (Investing.com, 2025). In the Indonesian shoe market, global brands still dominate, with Adidas (62.4%) and Nike (61.9%) at the top with nearly equal preference. This indicates that international brand strength remains a key factor in influencing purchasing decisions. Adidas' popularity is heavily influenced by promotions on TikTok, which have sparked high interest, especially among students, in impulsive product purchases simply to follow viral trends (Dini, 2025). This phenomenon demonstrates that social media interactions and digital promotions contribute to *brand growth. awareness* which ultimately drives purchasing decisions.

TikTok Shop's *interactive features*, such as *live-stream shopping*, *comments*, *likes*, and *real-time reviews*, create a more engaging shopping experience for consumers. This interactivity not only increases consumer engagement but also strengthens trust and emotional closeness to the brand. (Yanottama & Susila, 2025) Furthermore, digital promotion on TikTok is considered effective because it utilizes personalization algorithms, paid advertising, *influencers*, and creative campaigns such as *hashtag challenges* to reach a wider and faster audience (Miftahudin & Wahyudi, 2025). *Brand awareness* plays a crucial role as an intervening variable, bridging the influence of *TikTok Shop interactivity* and digital promotions on purchasing decisions. High levels of brand awareness make it easier for consumers to recognize, remember, and trust a product, making promotional messages and interactive experiences received through TikTok more effective in shaping long-term positive perceptions (Mughtar et al., 2022).

Figure 2 Distribution of Social Media Users by Gender in Indonesia

In Figure 2, Generation Z (Gen Z) shows the highest media consumption pattern among other generations, with an average duration reaching 6.6 hours per day in 2024. This reflects their heavy dependence on digital media, including social media, online videos, and other platforms, which have become an important part of their daily lives. As a generation that grew up with technology, Gen Z is highly connected to the digital world, which influences the way they interact, learn, and entertain themselves, making them the group with the most intense media engagement (Goodstats.id, 2024).

Figure 3 Population by Generation

Figure 3 shows the population proportion by generation, with a focus on the distribution of Gen Z, which reaches 31.25% of the total population. Given that Gen Z is a very important age group in various social and economic dynamics, the choice to focus on this generation in the city of Palu is very relevant. Gen Z in Palu City has great potential to drive change, especially in the fields of technology and entrepreneurship. As a digitally literate generation and concerned with social issues, they can play an active role in developing the digital economy and introducing new innovations. Although Palu is still in the development stage, focusing on Gen Z can help the city harness the great potential of the younger generation for more inclusive and sustainable growth (BPS, 2020).

Figure 4 Frequency of Social Media Access and Duration of Use in Indonesia

This is further reinforced by data from the second figure, which shows that TikTok still dominates as the most frequently accessed platform, followed by YouTube and Facebook. Furthermore, the duration of social media usage also shows that more than 14% of users access social media for more than 4 hours a day, with most of the time spent on platforms like TikTok and YouTube. This phenomenon illustrates how TikTok, initially known as an entertainment platform, has now transformed into an interactive space as well as a place for transactions through *TikTok Shop*, which is now attracting the attention of Gen Z as the main consumers (Kompas.com, 2025).

Given these developments, TikTok *Shop* has become a relevant research object for understanding consumer consumption behavior and digital interactions in the social media era. TikTok has evolved from a mere entertainment medium into an *e-commerce ecosystem* capable of facilitating consumer interaction and direct (Khoirunnisa et al., 2024) *online shopping transactions*. This condition reflects the transformation of consumer shopping behavior in the digital era, which increasingly relies on social media as a transactional space, a source of product information, and a means of considering purchases. Although previous studies have examined the influence of viral *marketing* and digital promotions on purchasing decisions, there are several gaps that have not been filled. One study Khansa & Khajar (2025) examined the influence of viral marketing on MSMEs with *brand awareness* as an intervening variable, but was limited to a local context. Meanwhile, Dewi & Aditama (2025) one analyzed the influence of digital promotions on Generation Z in TikTok *Shop*, but did not consider the role of *brand awareness* as a mediator. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by examining the influence of social media interactions through the TikTok *Shop feature* and digital promotions on purchasing decisions for Adidas products, with *brand awareness* as an intervening variable. This approach is important considering the characteristics of Adidas as a global brand that differs from MSMEs or local brands, so it is expected to provide broader theoretical and practical contributions in the context of interactive social media-based digital marketing in TikTok *Shop*. Based on the above description, this study focuses on how social media interactions through the TikTok *Shop feature* and digital promotions influence Adidas product purchasing decisions, as well as the extent to which *brand awareness* plays an intervening role in strengthening this relationship among Generation Z in Palu City. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of social media interactions and digital promotions on purchasing decisions, while also examining the role of *brand awareness* in mediating the influence of these two variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media Interaction

Kotler et al. (2024:44) states that social media is part of digital marketing that enables two-way communication between consumers and marketers to create *engagement*, long-term relationships, and mutual benefits. McQuail & Deuze (2020:38) This emphasizes that social media is more interactive than traditional mass media because it allows users to actively participate in creating and disseminating information, so that the roles between message creators and recipients become more balanced in the communication process. In line with that, Tovaes & Gordon (2021:3) it explains that social interaction in digital media shows a form of communication that involves the participation of users from various cultural backgrounds, which forms new identities, views, and social relationships, where users not only receive messages, but also play a role in determining the meaning of the message.

Thus, social media interaction can be understood as two-way communication based on digital technology that encourages active user involvement in creating, disseminating, and responding to content in a participatory manner without limitations of space and time. The dimensions of social media interaction in this study refer to Tovaes & Gordon (2021:171–198), namely active participation in digital activities, collaboration in content creation, the formation of digital trust and credibility between users, and the exchange of quality information that play an important role in building meaningful interactions on social media. Based on Ginting et al. (2023), the forms of social interaction on social media include information exchange, collaboration, introductions and social connections, two-way interactions, interactions through various forms of content, cross-cultural collaboration and ideas, creation of social identities, sharing experiences, and global discussions and conversations.

Digital Promotion

Digital promotion is an important part of modern marketing strategies that utilize digital technology to reach consumers more effectively. Kotler et al. (2024:514–517) states that digital promotion is part of the promotional mix that uses internet-based media and interactive technology to build relationships, create value, and strengthen two-way communication between companies and consumers. In line with that, Armstrong et al. (2023:464–466) explains that digital promotion includes the use of social media, *mobile devices*, interactive websites, and online *platforms* to communicate brand values and influence purchasing behavior personally and get direct responses. Thus, digital promotion can be understood as internet-based marketing communication and digital media that are interactive, measurable, and integrated, which not only convey information but also encourage engagement and build long-term relationships with consumers. The dimensions of digital promotion in this study refer to Kotler et al. (2024:514–518), which includes digital appeal in attracting consumer attention, consumer

engagement in promotional activities, conversion that encourages action and purchase commitment, and retention that reflects digital affinity and loyalty to the brand.

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is an important element in marketing strategy because the level of consumer awareness of a brand influences preferences, choices, and loyalty. Kotler et al. (2024:266–268) defines *brand awareness* as the ability of consumers to recognize (*brand recognition*) and recall (*brand recall*) a brand in a relevant product category, where high brand awareness increases the likelihood of the brand being considered when purchasing. Aaker (2020:90) also states that the higher the consumer's ability to recognize or recall a brand, the greater the chance of the brand being chosen over competitors. In line with that, Armstrong et al. (2023:232–233) explains that *brand awareness* is formed through consistent exposure to marketing messages, positive experiences, and repeated interactions with the brand, thus helping the brand occupy a certain position in the minds of consumers. Thus, *brand awareness* can be understood as the ability of consumers to recognize, remember, and identify a brand in a particular product category, which influences perceptions, preferences, and purchasing decisions. A high level of *brand awareness strengthens a brand's position in the market and increases the chances of choosing a brand over competitors. The dimensions of brand awareness* in this study refer to Aaker (2025:61–62) *brand recall*, *brand recognition*, and *top-of-mind awareness (TOMA)* as indicators of brand awareness in the minds of consumers.

Buying decision

Purchasing decisions are a series of stages consumers go through, from need recognition, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase decision, to post-purchase evaluation (Kotler et al., 2024:166–168). This process is psychological and influenced by internal factors such as motivation, perception, and attitude, as well as external factors such as culture, social environment, and the purchasing situation. (Armstrong et al., 2023:142–145) Thus, purchasing decisions are a complex process involving cognitive, emotional, and social interactions in determining consumer choice of a product or service. The dimensions of purchasing decisions in this study refer to (Kotler et al., 2024:166–170) *product choice*, *brand choice*, *distributor choice*, *purchase quantity*, *purchase time*, and *payment method*.

Hypothesis Development

1. According to research by Ghozahdi & Suharyati (2024), interactions through social media, particularly YouTube, have a positive and significant impact on *brand awareness*. Social media allows consumers to better recognize and remember brands, which can increase brand awareness.
H1: Social media interaction has a positive and significant effect on *brand awareness*.
2. Research conducted by Hasmawati & Zahara (2020) shown that social media, as part of digital promotion, has a significant impact on *brand awareness*. Marketing through digital platforms such as Instagram and TikTok has proven effective in introducing and increasing brand awareness among consumers.
H2: Digital promotion has a positive and significant effect on *brand awareness*.
3. Research by Khansa and Khajar (2025) shows that high *brand awareness can encourage consumers to make purchases. The stronger a consumer's awareness of a brand, the more likely they are to choose and purchase that product.*
H3: *Brand awareness* has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions.
4. Research Ghozahdi & Suharyati (2024) shows that interactions on social media not only increase *brand awareness* but can also directly influence purchasing decisions. Active interactions, such as sharing content and providing feedback, strengthen emotional connections with brands, ultimately driving purchasing decisions. In this research Rombe & Kristina Parinsi (2023), while the primary focus is on the marketing mix, consumer interactions through social media can play a significant role in introducing and influencing purchasing decisions.
H4: Social media interaction has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions.
5. Research by [Hasmawati & Zahara (2020)Entertainment] reveals that digital promotion through social media significantly influences purchasing decisions. Effective promotion through digital platforms like Instagram or TikTok can introduce products to consumers and influence their purchasing decisions.
H5: Digital promotion has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions.

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6. Research by Ghazahdi & Suharyati (2024), social media interactions have a direct impact on *brand awareness*, which then influences purchasing decisions. When consumers actively engage with brands on social media, their brand awareness increases, which ultimately contributes to purchasing decisions.
H6: Social media interaction has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions through *brand awareness*.
7. In research by Khansa and Khajar (2025), digital promotion was shown to increase *brand awareness*, which in turn influences purchasing decisions. When promotions are executed effectively through social media, they strengthen consumer brand awareness, ultimately influencing their purchasing decisions.
H7: Digital promotion has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions through *brand awareness*.

Figure 5 Research Framework

In the research framework diagram above, the existing lines have different meanings, namely:

- A straight line depicts a direct relationship or influence between one variable and another. In this case, the straight line between Social Media Interaction (X1) and *Brand Awareness* (Z) shows a direct influence of social media interaction on *brand awareness*. Digital Promotion (X2) and *Brand Awareness* (Z) show a direct influence of digital promotion on *brand awareness*. Likewise, there is a direct relationship between *brand awareness* and purchasing decisions (Y).
- Dotted lines indicate more complex or indirect relationships. For example, a dotted line connecting Social Media Interactions (X1) and Digital Promotions (X2) to Purchase Decisions (Y) via *Brand Awareness* (Z) could indicate that this relationship is being tested or that the hypothesis proposed is an indirect relationship.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method, namely an approach based on *the philosophy of positivism* with numerical data processing to test hypotheses statistically (Sugiyono, 2023:16). The object of the study is Generation Z in Palu City who have purchased Adidas products through *TikTok Shop*. The sampling technique used *purposive sampling*, with the following respondent criteria: being a Generation Z (born 1997–2012), and having purchased Adidas products through *TikTok Shop*. Data were collected through a questionnaire based on the variable indicators of social media interaction, digital promotion, *brand awareness* and purchasing decisions using a 1-5 point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The number of samples was determined by referring to Hair et al. (2021:161) which states that the number of samples can be calculated by multiplying the number of indicators by a minimum of five respondents. Based on this formula, the minimum number of samples required is $5 \times 34 = 170$ respondents. Validity and reliability tests were carried out using the SPSS application, while data analysis *Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling* (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS 4.0 to test the relationship between variables and the role of intervening variables (Hair et al., 2021:356). This method was chosen because it is able to analyze complex models and does not require normally distributed data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Data Characteristics

The presentation of respondent characteristics in this study aims to provide a general overview of those involved in the study. Information such as gender, year of birth, occupation, and frequency of TikTok use helps researchers ensure that the selected respondents align with the research objectives and understand the backgrounds that may influence how they seek information and make purchases of Adidas products through the TikTok Shop .

Table 1. Respondent Data Characteristics

Category Questions	Answer Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage%	
Gender	Man	49	28.8%	
	Woman	121	71.2%	
	Total	170	100%	
Year of birth	1997-2000	12	7.1%	
	2001-2004	132	77.6%	
	2005-2008	24	14.1%	
	2009-2012	2	1.2%	
	Total	170	100%	
Type of work	students	135	79.4%	
	Private sector employee	14	8.2%	
	civil servant	11	6.5%	
	Businessman	3	1.8%	
	Notary Public	1	0.6%	
	Housewife	1	0.6%	
	Indonesian National Police	1	0.6%	
	Indonesian National Armed Forces	1	0.6%	
	Self-employed	1	0.6%	
	Honorary	1	0.6%	
	Capster	1	0.6%	
	Total	100	100%	
	Frequency of TikTok Usage	every day	118	69.4%
		3-4 times a week	27	15.9%
1-2 times a week		25	14.7%	
Total	100	100%		

Source: Primary Data (2025)

This study involved 170 respondents who were active TikTok users and had purchased Adidas products through the TikTok Shop feature . The analysis results showed that the majority of respondents were female (71.2%), while 28.8% were male. This finding illustrates that Adidas product users on TikTok Shop are predominantly female, who are generally more active in following *fashion trends* , lifestyle, and digital promotions on social media. Based on occupation, the majority of respondents were students (79.4%), followed by private employees (8.2%), civil servants (6.5%), and entrepreneurs (1.8%) and other professions such as notaries, housewives, police officers, military personnel, self-employed, honorary workers, and hairdressers, each with 0.6%. This composition shows that active Adidas product users on TikTok Shop have diverse professional backgrounds, but the majority are young people who actively use social media as a means of information and product purchases. In addition, the majority of respondents use TikTok every day (69.4%), which indicates the high intensity of user interaction with the features and digital promotional content on the platform. All respondents (100%) stated that they had purchased Adidas products through TikTok Shop , so the selection of respondents was considered appropriate to the research context.

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

Figure 6. Outer Loading

The model shown in this figure illustrates the direct and indirect influences between variables, where social media interactions and digital promotions influence brand awareness, which in turn influences consumer purchasing decisions. The results of this model provide insight into how digital factors play a role in influencing purchasing decisions by increasing brand awareness.

Convergent Validity Test (Outer Loading)

The table below is used to ensure that each indicator truly represents the construct it measures. In PLS-SEM, convergent validity is assessed through the *outer loading value*, where a value above 0.70 is considered to indicate that the indicator has a good contribution to the construct. According to a high Hair et al. (2021) *outer loading value*, the indicator is relevant and appropriate in describing the construct being studied. Thus, the convergent validity test helps researchers ensure that the instrument used has adequate measurement quality and can be trusted in further analysis.

Table 2. Convergent Validity Test

Social Media Interaction	Digital Promotion	Brand awareness	Buying decision
IMS1 (0.848)	PD1 (0.899)	BA1 (0.921)	KP1 (0.881)
IMS2 (0.857)	PD2 (0.907)	BA2 (0.900)	KP10 (0.908)
IMS3 (0.861)	PD3 (0.854)	BA3 (0.891)	KP11 (0.908)
IMS4 (0.826)	PD4 (0.795)	BA4 (0.872)	KP12 (0.809)
IMS5 (0.888)	PD5 (0.835)	BA5 (0.896)	KP2 (0.877)
IMS6 (0.885)	PD6 (0.882)	BA6 (0.922)	KP3 (0.900)
IMS7 (0.884)	PD7 (0.909)		KP4 (0.943)
IMS8 (0.889)	PD8 (0.923)		KP5 (0.906)
			KP6 (0.904)
			KP7 (0.873)
			KP8 (0.878)
			KP9 (0.793)

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

Based on the analysis results in the outer loading table, all indicators in the variables of Social Media Interaction, Digital Promotion, *Brand Awareness*, and Purchase Decisions show outer loading values above 0.70, with most even exceeding 0.80. This indicates that each statement in the questionnaire is considered valid and able to measure the variables well. Thus, no indicators need to be eliminated, because all meet the convergence criteria. This good convergent validity strengthens that each construct has a strong relationship between the indicators and its variables.

Discriminant Validity Test: Fornel & Larcker

According to Hair et al. (2021) the discriminant validity test, it is used to ensure that each construct in the model is truly different from each other and does not measure the same concept. Discriminant validity is important because it shows that a construct has unique characteristics compared to other constructs, so that the analysis results do not experience overlapping meanings between variables. One method commonly used is the Fornell & Larcker criterion, namely by comparing the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct with its correlation with other constructs. If the square root of the AVE value is greater than the

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correlation between constructs, then the construct is considered to have adequate discriminant validity. Thus, the discriminant validity test helps researchers ensure that each construct in the PLS-SEM model has clear conceptual boundaries and can be analyzed separately without influencing each other.

Table 3. Results of the Discriminant Validity Test (Fornel & Lacker Criteria)

	Brand Awareness (Z)	Social Media Interaction (X1)	Purchase Decision (Y)	Digital Promotion (X2)
Brand Awareness (Z)	0.900			
Social Media Interaction (X1)	0.535	0.868		
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.790	0.733	0.883	
Digital Promotion (X2)	0.519	0.507	0.700	0.876

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

The results in the table show that all variables have high values, thus being considered strong and reliable in describing the research construct. Social Media Interaction (0.868) and Digital Promotion (0.876) indicate that the indicators are able to explain the quality of interaction and the effectiveness of promotions through TikTok well. *Brand Awareness* has the highest value, at 0.900, indicating very strong Adidas brand awareness among respondents. Meanwhile, Purchase Decision obtained a value of 0.883, so the indicator is considered good and consistent. Overall, all variables have met the eligibility criteria for analysis in the next stage.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing is used to ensure that each indicator within a construct is capable of providing consistent measurement results. Hair et al. (2021) Good reliability indicates that the items within a variable are interrelated and work stably in measuring the same concept. In PLS-SEM, reliability is assessed through Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and rho_A, where high values indicate that the instrument is trustworthy and suitable for use in analysis. Thus, reliability testing helps researchers ensure that the data obtained is of adequate quality before further model testing.

Table 4. Reliability Test

Construct/ Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Social Media Interaction	0.953	0.955	0.961	0.753
Digital Promotion	0.957	0.959	0.964	0.768
Brand awareness	0.953	0.954	0.963	0.811
Buying decision	0.974	0.976	0.977	0.779

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

The reliability test results indicate that all variables are highly reliable and valid. The Cronbach's Alpha values for Social Media Interaction (0.953), Digital Promotion (0.957), *Brand Awareness* (0.953), and Purchase Decision (0.974) are above 0.70, indicating that all constructs are reliable. The Composite Reliability values are also high, namely (0.961), (0.964), (0.963), and (0.977), respectively, strengthening internal consistency. In addition, the AVE value for each variable (0.753; 0.768; 0.811; 0.779) is > 0.50, indicating that convergent validity is met. With these results, all instruments are suitable for use in subsequent analyses.

Inner Model R-Square Test

The R-Square test on the inner model is used to determine how much the independent variables can explain the dependent variable in a research model. The Hair et al. (2021) R-Square value indicates how strongly several variables influence the predicted variable. The higher the value, the better the model's ability to explain the phenomenon under study. Therefore, the R- Square test helps researchers understand how well the structural model works and whether the relationships between the tested variables have adequate predictive power.

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Table 5. R-Square Test Results

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Brand awareness	0.369	0.361
Buying decision	0.814	0.811

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

The R-Square test results show that *the Brand Awareness variable* has an R-Square value of 0.369, which means that *Brand Awareness* can be explained by Social Media Interaction and Digital Promotion by 36.9%. Thus, it can be concluded that the model has a fairly good explanatory ability for the *Brand Awareness variable*. Meanwhile, the purchasing decision variable has an R-Square value of 0.814, which means that the purchasing decision can be explained by Social Media Interaction, Digital Promotion, and *Brand Awareness* by 81.4%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model has a strong explanatory ability for the purchasing decision variable.

Hypothesis Testing

testing Hair et al. (2021) is used to determine whether the relationship between variables in a research model is truly supported by the data. Through statistical tests such as the *t-statistic* and *p-value*, researchers can assess whether the influence of one variable on another is significant or simply occurs by chance. Hypothesis testing helps ensure that the relationships established in a theoretical model have a strong empirical basis. In the context of PLS-SEM, testing is conducted by examining the magnitude of the path coefficient *and* its significance. If the *p-value* is below the threshold (generally 0.05), the relationship is considered significant and the hypothesis is accepted. Thus, hypothesis testing serves to validate the developed structural model and ensure that the research conclusions are scientifically sound.

Table 6. Hypothesis Test Results

Relationship between variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
Social Media Interaction (X1) -> Brand Awareness (Z)	0.366	0.362	0.114	3,200	0.001
Digital Promotion (X2) -> Brand Awareness (Z)	0.333	0.339	0.108	3,071	0.002
Brand Awareness (Z) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.457	0.460	0.091	5,025	0.000
Social Media Interaction (X1) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.342	0.335	0.080	4,253	0.000
Digital Promotion (X2) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.289	0.288	0.076	3,795	0.000
Social Media Interaction (X1) -> Brand Awareness (Z) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.167	0.170	0.071	2,343	0.019
Digital Promotion (X2) -> Brand Awareness (Z) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.152	0.158	0.063	2,415	0.016

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2025)

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in Table 6, all relationships between variables in this study were proven to have a positive and significant effect. Social Media Interaction has a significant effect on *Brand Awareness* (O = 0.366; *p* = 0.001), which indicates that the higher the intensity of user interaction on social media, the greater their awareness of the brand. Digital Promotion also has a positive and significant effect on *Brand Awareness* (O = 0.333; *p* = 0.002), which indicates that an effective digital promotion strategy can increase the level of brand awareness by consumers.

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Furthermore, *Brand Awareness* is proven to have a strong and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions ($O = 0.457$; $p = 0.000$), so that the higher the consumer awareness of a brand, the greater their tendency to make a purchase. Social Media Interaction also has a positive and significant direct influence on Purchasing Decisions ($O = 0.342$; $p = 0.000$), indicating that consumer activity and engagement on social media can drive purchasing decisions. Similarly, Digital Promotion is proven to have a significant influence on Purchasing Decisions ($O = 0.289$; $p = 0.000$). In addition to its direct influence, the results of this study also indicate that *Brand Awareness* plays a role as a mediating variable. This is evidenced by the mediating influence of Social Media Interaction on Purchasing Decisions through *Brand Awareness* ($O = 0.167$; $p = 0.019$), as well as the mediating influence of Digital Promotion on Purchasing Decisions through *Brand Awareness* ($O = 0.152$; $p = 0.016$). This means that social media interaction and digital promotion will be more effective in driving purchasing decisions if they are able to first increase consumer *Brand Awareness*. Thus, all hypotheses proposed in this study are declared accepted, because all relationships between variables are proven to be significant based on the results of the SEM-PLS 4.0 analysis.

Discussion

The results of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the influence of social media interactions and digital promotions on purchasing decisions for Adidas products through TikTok Shop, with brand awareness as a mediating variable among Generation Z in Palu City. These findings reinforce those of Kotler et al. (2024), who stated that modern social media functions not only as a marketing communication channel but also as an interactive space that simultaneously shapes consumer experiences and perceptions. The significant influence of social media interaction on brand awareness is in line with research Ghozahdi & Suharyati (2024) who found that active consumer engagement on social media increases brand recognition and recall through two-way communication. Similar findings were also expressed by Rombe & Kristina (2023) which confirms that digital social interactions can build stronger brand associations than one-way marketing communications. Thus, this research confirms that social media interactions are not simply communication activities, but rather a cognitive mechanism for building brand awareness.

The research results showing the significant influence of digital promotion on brand awareness support the findings. Hasmawati & Zahara (2020) which states that consistent and relevant digital promotions, tailored to the characteristics of social media platforms, can increase brand exposure and recall. The study Armstrong et al. (2023) also confirms that visual and interactive formats in digital promotions play a significant role in strengthening brand recall among young consumers. Therefore, these findings expand the empirical evidence that digital promotions not only impact short-term sales but also contribute to the formation of long-term brand assets. The significant influence of brand awareness on purchasing decisions is consistent with research Aaker (2020) that places brand awareness as a key element of brand equity that influences consumer preferences and beliefs. This finding is also in line with Khansa & Khajar (2025) who found that consumers with high levels of brand awareness tend to be more confident in making purchasing decisions, particularly in the context of online shopping. Thus, brand awareness functions as a perceptual risk reducer and a determinant of brand choice.

The direct influence of social media interactions on purchasing decisions strengthens the findings of Ghozahdi and Suharyati (2024) who stated that interactive experiences on social media are able to build emotional attachments and encourage rapid purchasing decisions. McQuail & Deuze (2020) also emphasized that the participatory nature of digital media allows consumers to play an active role in the meaning-making process, so that purchasing decisions are not always preceded by a lengthy evaluation process. These findings suggest that social media interactions have immediate persuasive power. Furthermore, the significant influence of digital promotions on purchasing decisions is in line with findings Hasmawati & Zahara (2020) stating that digital promotions can function as a trigger for purchasing actions through special offers and visual appeal. Kotler et al. (2024) Kotler et al. (2024) also explain that digital promotions tailored to social media user behavior can accelerate consumer decision-making. Thus, digital promotions act as a stimulus that encourages an instant purchasing response. The results of the indirect effect test indicate that brand awareness mediates the relationship between social media interactions and purchasing decisions. This finding is consistent with research by Rombe and Kristina (2023), who found that brand awareness acts as an intervening variable in the relationship between social media activity and purchasing behavior. Research by Ghozahdi and Suharyati (2024) also confirmed that social media interactions first shape brand awareness before driving purchasing decisions. Thus, brand awareness serves as a psychological link between digital stimuli and consumer responses.

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Similar findings also apply to the relationship between digital promotions and purchasing decisions through brand awareness. These results support research by Khansa and Khajar (2025), which states that the effectiveness of digital promotions increases when they build strong brand awareness. These findings indicate that digital promotions not only directly impact purchasing decisions but also indirectly by shaping consumer perceptions and beliefs about a brand. Based on the analysis of the relationships between variables, it can be concluded that brand awareness is the most influential variable on purchasing decisions for Adidas products through TikTok Shop among Generation Z in Palu City. A high level of brand awareness makes consumers have stronger confidence, trust, and positive perceptions of the product, thus encouraging faster and more confident purchasing decisions. Although social media interactions and digital promotions both play important roles as triggers, their influence on purchasing decisions becomes more significant when they are able to build brand awareness first. Thus, these findings indicate that the success of a digital marketing strategy on TikTok Shop is largely determined by its ability to strengthen brand awareness as the main foundation that directs consumer purchasing behavior.

Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) theory put forward by Mehrabian and Russell (1974) Based on this theory, social media interactions through the *TikTok Shop feature* and digital promotions act as *stimuli* that influence consumers' internal psychological states, such as *brand awareness*, which functions as an organism. High *brand awareness increases positive perceptions of the brand and strengthens emotional connections with the product, which in turn influences consumer responses* or behavior, namely purchasing decisions. In other words, *stimuli* in the form of intensive social interactions and digital promotions can create emotional experiences that lead to stronger brand awareness and ultimately encourage consumers to make purchases, according to the findings obtained in this study. Overall, the findings of this study confirm that social media engagement and digital promotion strategies through *TikTok Shop* are effective in increasing *brand awareness* and driving purchasing decisions for Adidas products among Gen Z in Palu City. TikTok serves not only as an entertainment *platform* but also as an interactive marketing space that directly shapes consumer perceptions, experiences, and purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that social media interactions and digital promotions have a positive and significant influence on *brand awareness* and purchasing decisions for Adidas products among Generation Z in Palu City. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that social media interactions and digital promotions have a positive effect on *brand awareness* with a significant path coefficient. In addition, *brand awareness* was proven to have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, supporting the proposed hypothesis. The direct effect of social media interactions and digital promotions on purchasing decisions was also found to be significant, in accordance with the tested hypothesis. Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that social media interactions and digital promotions have an indirect effect on purchasing decisions through *brand awareness*, which strengthens *the role of brand awareness* as a mediator in the relationship between the variables. Overall, these findings confirm that social media interactions and digital promotions can more effectively influence purchasing decisions if they can first increase consumer *brand awareness*. Therefore, social media-based digital marketing strategies, especially through platforms like TikTok, can be utilized to build strong *brand awareness* and drive purchasing decisions.

These findings provide important insights for marketers targeting Generation Z in Palu City. Marketing that prioritizes social media interactions and digital promotions, especially through TikTok, can be a highly effective strategy for increasing *brand awareness* and influencing purchasing decisions. Therefore, companies like Adidas should utilize *TikTok Shop* and creative content that can increase consumer engagement, to strengthen *brand awareness* and drive product purchasing decisions. Theoretically, the results of this study strengthen the understanding of the role of social media interactions and digital promotions in building brand awareness and influencing purchasing decisions, especially among Generation Z. This study also contributes to the development of a model of the relationship between social media, digital promotions, *brand awareness*, and purchasing decisions, which can serve as a basis for further research in the field of digital marketing and consumer behavior.

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